

An Evaluation of OpenAlex:
Exploring the Level 0 'Geology' Concept Hierarchy

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1 Introduction

OpenAlex is a free index of hundreds of millions journals, databases, etc. across the world consolidated into one location, inspired by the ancient Library of Alexandria. The works catalogued by OpenAlex can be searched and sorted through using multiple categories including by author, venue, institution, work, or concept. This group project intends to evaluate the effectiveness of using OpenAlex's concepts to locate relevant works by exploring and assessing the Level 0 concept 'Geology' and its associated hierarchy of concepts.

2 Literature review and environmental scan

Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG) was a database of scholarly and academic publications. According to Wang et al., MAG had a critical role in the transition from traditional manual curation to automated data collection and processing in regard to academic knowledge organization (2019). MAG was deeply ingrained in various research processes (Tay et al., 2021) and therefore raised substantial concerns within the academic sphere as Microsoft announced discontinuing its support for MAG. Shortly after, the OpenAlex (OA) project emerged as a seamless replacement. OpenAlex is a valuable open scholarly database that is still evolving (Schares & Mierz, 2023). OpenAlex categorizes scholarly entities into five primary types: works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts (Priem et al., 2022). Each entity type "has its own endpoint that can be queried using a variety of filters to specify a desired subset" (Schares & Mierz, 2023). OpenAlex contains roughly 250M scholarly works which encompass a variety of scholarly documents such as journal articles, books, datasets, and theses. Each work is identified by an internal identifier, known as the OpenAlex ID, which connects the work to other works (Priem et al., 2022, Schares & Mierz, 2023).

Authors, defined as "people who create works" (Priem et al., 2022) are indexed at approximately 213 million, with daily additions. OpenAlex uses ORCID, authors' publication records, and citation histories to help disambiguate authors of more recent works. Accurate author identification is crucial for tracking academic contributions and assessing research impact (Wang et al., 2019). This is a common and persistent challenge and concern in academic databases and was addressed in MAG. MAG created profiles for authors based on their publications, and machine learning techniques were used to distinguish between authors with similar names which improved the accuracy of authorship attributions (Wang et al., 2019). As OpenAlex has MAG as its foundation, it is no surprise that OA also aims to improve author disambiguation and provide a more accurate representation of scholarly contributions by different authors. OpenAlex therefore tries to contribute to the accuracy and reliability of academic databases, supporting researchers in their pursuit of comprehensive and precise academic knowledge.

OpenAlex keeps track of 109.000 institutions which are organizations where authors are connected. 94% of these institutions have ROR IDs as their Canonical External IDs. The fourth type, venues, are described as the hosts of works (Priem et al., 2022). There are approximately 124.000 venues ranging from journals, conferences, preprint repositories, and institutional repositories (2022). These venues play a crucial role in the dissemination and accessibility of scholarly knowledge and serve to accommodate the varying needs and

preferences of authors and researchers by offering a diverse environment for the presentation and publication of works. Information about the organizations to which authors belong, known as institutions, are also widely listed by OpenAlex. In fact, around 109,000 institutions are indexed using sources like PubMed and involving machine-learning techniques to organize the data, echoing MAG's approach (Priem et al., 2022).

The final category, concepts, is crucial in organizing and categorizing scholarly knowledge within academic databases. The concepts in OpenAlex are part of a hierarchical tree (Priem et al., 2022) and "each concept is a collection of semantic representations of textual passages, and these abstract representations, though not readable to humans, are adequate for machine reasoning" (Wang et al., 2019). MAG had an extensive dataset for academic research, covering a range of concepts. This focus on concepts is a feature shared with OpenAlex which aims to enhance transparency and accessibility in scholarly metadata (Priem et al., 2022). Around 65,000 concepts are indexed in OpenAlex, which presumably are ensured to have complete compatibility with Wikidata concepts which OpenAlex assigns using Wikidata IDs as Canonical External IDs (CEID). OpenAlex adopts a modified version of MAG's hierarchical approach to concepts. The 65,000 concepts in OpenAlex are structured hierarchically with 19 root-level concepts and five layers of descendants. In this way, OpenAlex builds upon MAG's concept-based approach to potentially advance the organization and accessibility of academic knowledge, while introducing a structured hierarchy that tailors concept assignments to scholarly works.

OpenAlex also builds upon MAG's concept-based approach to subject classifications but it reduces the number of Fields of Study (FoS) "by removing those with less than 500 papers associated" (Scheidsteger et al., 2022). This change in FoS structure is significant and affects the precision of categorization within academic databases. There is some consistency between the two databases. For instance, all 19 top-level FoS from MAG remained (Scheidsteger et al., 2022). However, the transition from MAG to OpenAlex led to a substantial decrease beyond level two FoS, where only less than 10% of MAG remained. The study conducted by Scheidsteger et al., also revealed that even though top-level FoS were retained, they were differently associated with papers in OpenAlex compared to MAG. Researchers conducting bibliometric analyses need to be aware of these shifts and changes and their impact on the precision of subject classification in academic databases as they potentially affect the accuracy and reliability of subject categorization due to the fact that FoS plays a critical role in determining the categorization and accessibility of academic knowledge in databases like OpenAlex (Scheidsteger et al., 2022).

Through the exploration and use of the historical MAG data set, OpenAlex attempted to develop a model which resembles the MAG concept tagger in order to tag academic papers with relevant topics and concepts. The multi-class deep learning classifier was developed as a concept tagger with presumably high precision "because if a paper is tagged with a concept, it is important that the tag is correct" (Priem et al., 2022). In order to attain accuracy with concept tagging, OpenAlex created the model while considering factors such as paper title, document type, journal title, and abstracts (Priem et al., 2022).

A number of other papers have used OpenAlex in their research and have found it rather useful, despite certain complications. A study conducted by Kwon et al. (2023), which examined how the COVID-19 pandemic impacted research productivity in terms of gender disparities and correlated this with factors such as author characteristics and the research environment found it "challenging to combine it with MAG because OpenAlex collects

metadata using a different methodology”. Another study conducted by Szymula et al. (2023) used OpenAlex to explore the relationship between gender and open-access publishing. The researchers claimed that OpenAlex’s comprehensive data enabled them to investigate publishing patterns within scientific areas and gain insights into the publication trends of male and female scientists. The data from OpenAlex appears to have facilitated a discipline-specific analysis.

Furthermore, Schares & Mierz. conducted a study on the development of an open and reproducible process for extracting cited reference data (2023) in which OpenAlex API was used to “collect, clean, and examine one year’s worth of open-cited reference data from Iowa State University-authored publications” (Schares & Mierz, 2023). While the authors encountered some complications with citation data, as it was not openly available for every publication in OpenAlex, the authors still found that the database’s API enabled efficient querying and retrieval of publication metadata and they were able to access the necessary data for the analysis (Schares & Mierz, 2023). While OpenAlex proved to be a useful source for understanding characteristics of cited references by researchers, citation data seemed to be somewhat problematic as the database can only return data it is aware of (Schares & Mierz, 2023).

3 Evaluation

3.1 Evaluation of the classification system

3.1.1 Quantitative analysis

The intent of the quantitative analysis of the classification system is to determine in numbers the classifications at each level and the relationships between the classifications at each level for the Level 0 concept of ‘Geology’.

3.1.1.1 Methodology

The quantitative analysis was completed using the excel breakdown spreadsheet of the OpenAlex classification system. The spreadsheet includes information such as level, concept name, and concept parents. Since the excel sheet is a downloaded version of the entire online OpenAlex classification system, some changes must be made before quantitative analysis can be performed for the field of geology.

Due to how the parent concepts are displayed online, in the excel sheet they are grouped together in a single cell separated by semicolons. The first change made was to separate out the parent concepts into individual columns labelled parent 1, parent 2, etc. Next, the second change was to separate the comprehensive sheet into separate sheets for each Level 0 through Level 5.

Since the spreadsheet is an overview of the classification system as a whole and the focus of this paper is geology, the third change was to separate out the concepts at each level stemming from the Level 0 concept of ‘Geology’. To do so, the “if” and “and” functions in Excel were used to filter out terms at each level which fell into the category of geology. To determine what qualifies as being in the field of geology the following logic is applied. For

Level 1, any term with a minimum of one parent term being the concept of geology. For Level 2 and above, any term with a minimum of one parent term being any geology concept from the level above it.

Once the spreadsheet had been restructured such that there were separate sheets for each level of the classification system, solely containing terms falling under the Level 0 term of 'Geology', it was possible to use formulas in Excel to perform the quantitative analysis.

3.1.1.2 Results

The first step of the quantitative analysis of the OpenAlex classification system was to look at the number of concepts at the level in the field of geology. Table 1 below shows the number of concepts at each level under 'Geology' compared to the total number of concepts at each level.

Table 1
Number of Concepts in Field of Geology

Level	Number of Concepts in Field of Geology	Total Number of Concepts	Number of Concepts in Field of Geology as a Percentage of the Total Number of Concepts
0	1	19	5.26%
1	17	284	5.99%
2	1333	21455	6.21%
3	1916	24749	7.74%
4	855	1395	61.29%
5	255	6124	4.16%

Looking at the column showing the number of concepts in the field of geology as a percentage of the total number of concepts, the percentage at Level 4 is indicative of a problem within the classification system. Since 'Geology' is 1 of 19 Level 0 concepts, theoretically the percentage of the total should remain around the same at each level since the entire classification system is growing at each level. This is the case for Levels 0-3 and Level 5 which are all hovering around 6%, however, Level 4 sees a dramatic increase up to 61.29%.

There are two explanations for this dramatic increase. The first is that most other Level 0 concept fields stopped growing at Level 3. This explanation is unlikely as there is a jump back down to a small percentage at Level 5. The second and more likely explanation is that there is an issue with the hierarchical structure of the classification system. It is possible that there have been relationship links made to many other Level 0 concepts, which results in concepts that should fall under a different Level 0 concept now appearing to fall under 'Geology'. This explanation indicates a significant issue with the OpenAlex classification system as there should not be overlap in a proper hierarchy.

From this first step of analysis, it is apparent that there are issues with the OpenAlex classification system. To see what kind of issues there are, we will look at the parent-child relationships in the classification system. First by looking at the parents of each concept at each level and then by looking at the children of each concept at each level.

The second step of the analysis is to look at the number of parent concepts at each level, both in the field of geology and of the classification system as a whole as a point of

comparison. Table 2 below shows the total number of parent concepts at each level as well as the number of unique parent concepts at each level.

Table 2
Number of Parent Concepts at Each Level

Level	Total Parent Concepts	Unique Parent Concepts
0	0	0
1	27	7
2	3320	137
3	3798	857
4	1363	428
5	400	139

Theoretically, the total number of parent concepts should be the same as the total number of concepts in the field of geology at each level (shown in the previous table) because, in a true hierarchical system, each concept has a single parent concept. Looking at the total number of parent concepts in the field of geology we can see that it is greater than the total number of concepts in the field of geology which indicates a problem.

Additionally, looking at the number of unique concepts in the field of geology, theoretically, the number should be equal to or less than the total number of concepts in the level above. Looking at Level 1, we know that there should only be one parent concept as the only concept in the field of geology at Level 0 is 'Geology'. However, the data shows that there are 7 unique parent terms which means that we have links to six other Level 0 concepts.

The issues seen with both the total number of parent concepts in the field of geology and the number of unique parent concepts in the field of geology indicate that OpenAlex has classified terms with multiple parent concepts spamming multiple fields. The third step was to determine how many parent terms we are seeing at each level in the field of geology. The data on the number of parent terms for each concept is shown in Table 3. The blacked out cells in the table indicate that that cell is not applicable to that level.

Table 3
Number of Parent Concepts at Each Level

Level	1 Parent	2 Parent	3 Parent	4 Parent	5 Parent	6 Parent	7 Parent
0							
1	7	10					
2	93	504	729	3	4		
3	802	618	298	140	42	13	3
4	520	215	80	29	9	2	
5	180	36	18	14	4	3	

This data shows that at every level with parent concepts, there is the issue of having multiple parent concepts for a single child concept. This further illustrates issues with the OpenAlex classification system.

Since we know there are issues with concepts having links to other fields, the fourth step was to determine the number of parent concepts actually in the field of geology at each level. Theoretically it should be all of them, but based on the analysis thus far that is most likely not the case. Table 4 shows the number of unique parent concepts in the field of geology, both as a number per level and as a percentage of the total number of unique parents.

Table 4*Number of Unique Parent Concepts at Each Level in the Field of Geology*

Level	Number of Unique Parents in Field of Geology	Number of Unique Parents in Field of Geology as a Percentage of the Total Number of Unique Parents
0	0	0.00%
1	1	14.29%
2	17	12.41%
3	356	41.54%
4	339	79.21%
5	119	85.61%

As suspected, not all of the parent terms at each level fall into the field of geology. Had that been the case, the percentage would have been 100% at each level. Looking at the percentage, it would appear as though the classification issues of linking to other Level 0 concepts resolves itself in the lower levels of the classification system as we are seeing percentages closer to 100%. However, that is likely not the case but rather a skewed view of the classification system. At the higher levels there are a large number of terms with parents outside the field of geology, as a result their children will all also appear to be geology related. As we descend further in the levels of the classification system we are seeing a higher quantity of terms that incorrectly appear to be geology related which results in the higher percentages in the lower levels.

As one may expect, if not all parent terms are in the field of geology then concepts at each level will have links to other Level 0 concepts. The fifth step was to determine how many concepts have links to other Level 0 concepts and what are those Level 0 concepts. Table 5 below shows how many concepts have links to other Level 0 concepts.

Table 5*Number of Concepts with Links to Level 0 Concepts Other Than Geology at Each Level*

Level	Number of Concepts with Links to Other Level 0 Concepts	Number of Concepts with Links to Other Level 0 Concepts as a Percentage of Total Geology Concepts
0	0	0.00%
1	10	58.82%
2	1082	81.17%
3	842	43.95%
4	139	16.26%
5	22	8.63%

The large numbers of overlap as seen in the table indicates significant problems with the OpenAlex classification system and a failure in the hierarchical structure.

Looking at Level 1, we can get a good overview of which other Level 0 concepts with which geology overlaps. At Level 1, aside from geology we are seeing additional parent terms of physics, geography, engineering, chemistry, biology, and environmental science. All of the concepts with which there is overlap are STEM terms in the field of science which makes them logical terms for overlap and indicates that while there are issues they aren't so widespread as if there were to be links to sociology or philosophy.

Since we've looked at the parent concepts at each level, the next step in evaluating the parent-child relationships in the OpenAlex classification system is to look in depth about the children of each concept at each level. The sixth step is to look at the number of concepts at each level with no child concepts, which is presented in Table 6.

Table 6*Number of Concepts at Each Level with no Further Children*

Level	Number of Concepts with no Further Children	Number of Concepts with no Further Children as a Percentage of Total Geology Concepts
0	0	0.00%
1	0	0.00%
2	977	73.29%
3	1577	82.31%
4	736	86.08%
5	255	100.00%

From the data, it is apparent that past Level 1 the majority of terms don't have children. As a result, lower level concepts will be heavily skewed towards the terms that have children. This means that the breadth of concepts in the lower levels won't fully capture the field of geology.

As we decrease in level the concepts get increasingly more specified. Since Level 2 is still fairly general in the grand scheme of the hierarchy, it seems strange that 73% of the concepts at this level do not have a subfield warranting a child term. This indicates another issue in the classification system and it's likely that rather than these concepts not existing, they've instead been classified incorrectly and appear somewhere else entirely.

Thinking back to the analysis of the parent terms at each level, we saw that at each level there were more parents than children. Considering, the majority of concepts do not have children this must mean that some of the concepts have an extremely large number of children. The seventh step was to look at the number of children of each concept. Table 7 below shows the number of concepts with one child, more than one child, and the highest number of children at each level.

Table 7*Number of Concepts at Each Level with Multiple Children*

Level	Number of Concepts with One Child	Number of Concepts with More than One Child	Highest Number of Child Concepts Held by any One Parent
0	0	1	17
1	0	17	637
2	126	230	294
3	158	181	34
4	60	59	19
5	0	0	0

Looking at the data it is apparent that many terms do only have one child but also that just as many have multiple children. This is as expected for a hierarchical classification system and doesn't indicate a significant problem as have many of the other sections of the analysis.

However, what may be an issue is the quantity of children held by some parents. Looking at Level 2, the highest number of children is 637 which will result in skewing the lower levels towards this concept. This in itself is not an issue as it is possible that that is a defining theory in geology resulting in many children. The issue stems from the more widespread classification issues. The trickle down effect will mean that if the concept with 637 children overlaps with another Level 0 concept, then all 637 children will have the same overlap. This will have the effect of perpetuating the issue of overlap between Level 0 concepts.

Going back to the idea of having incorrectly classified terms, the final step was to look at the classification system as a whole to see if there were any concepts at each level with no parent terms, which is shown in Table 8.

Table 8

Number of Concepts at Each Level with No Parent Concepts

Level	Number of Concepts with no Parent	Number of Concepts with no Parent as a Percentage of Total OA Concepts
0	19	100.00%
1	0	0.00%
2	221	1.03%
3	1554	6.28%
4	289	20.72%
5	122	1.99%

Theoretically, the only level with no parents should be Level 0. However, as visible in Table 8, that is not the case. As we saw many of the concepts at each level have no children and as discussed the issue may be that in reality they have child concepts but OpenAlex has incorrectly classified them. It is possible that some of these unclaimed terms are those incorrectly classified terms and should fall somewhere in the field of geology. Additionally, as with the majority of the analysis, having concepts with no parent indicates a failure in the hierarchy and issues with the OpenAlex classification.

In conclusion, it is highly likely that the issues experienced with the OpenAlex classification of 'Geology' are a systematic issue extending to all of the other Level 0 concepts. Considering the magnitude of the problems and how they lead to the failure of the hierarchical system these issues should be remedied.

3.1.2 Qualitative analysis

3.1.2.1 Methodology

In order to perform the qualitative analysis it was necessary to decide which sections of the OpenAlex classification of 'Geology' to evaluate. OpenAlex includes 17 Level 1 concepts, of which their parent concept is 'Geology' and respectively 1333, 1916, 855, and 255 of Levels 2, 3, 4 and 5. As it is very hard to go through all the 4377 concepts, the decision was made to evaluate all 17 Level 1 concepts and then pick a sample concept's children to evaluate the subsequent levels.

To qualitatively evaluate the 17 Level 1 concepts, we needed to refer to an accurate classification system. The *U.S. Geological Survey Library Classification System* (Sasscer, 2010) has been designated as a comparative earth science library, which is a tool for assigning classification numbers to earth science and allied pure science library materials in order to collect these materials into related subject groups. The classification scheme has been developed over the years since 1904. We selected this classification system at the recommendation of a subject matter expert in a field related to biology and geology. The subject classification schedule has three main divisions: general works, earth sciences, and pure sciences. Table 9 shows the principle classes.

Table 9*Principal Classes of the U.S. Geological Survey Library Classification System*

Subject Classification	Class Number	Includes
General Works	001-095	Science, Computer science, Information systems, Bibliography, Directories, Dictionaries, and Biography
Earth Sciences	101-190	Mineralogy and Petrology
	201-298	General geology, Geologic hazards, Tectonics, Structural geology, Geophysics, and Geochemistry
	301-371	Historical and Stratigraphic geology
	401-471	Mineral resources, Mineral industries, and Mining
	501-590	Geography/geomorphology, Meteorology, Landforms, and Oceanography
	601-699	Palaeontology
Pure Sciences	701-795	Mathematics, Astronomy, Geodesy, Engineering, and Hydrology
	801-895	Physics and Chemistry
	901-999	General biology, Ecology, Evolution, Botany, Agriculture, Forestry, and Zoology

Based on the classifications shown in Table 9, benchmarking was used to evaluate the relevance and accuracy of the OpenAlex classification system.

3.1.2.2 Results

Using the *U.S. Geological Survey library classification system* as previously shown in Table 9 we have tried to evaluate the seventeen Level 1 concepts as relevant (R) or Not Relevant (NR). Table 10 shows results of the evaluation of the Level 1 concepts under 'Geology'.

Table 10*Level 1 Concepts under Level 0 Geology*

Concept	Parent Concept(s)	Relevance
Atmospheric sciences	Geology, Physics	R
Climatology	Geology	R
Earth science	Geology	R
Geochemistry	Geology	R
Geodesy	Geography, Geology	NR - Branch of geophysics
Geomorphology	Geology	R
Geophysics	Geology, Physics	R
Geotechnical engineering	Engineering, Geology	R
Mineralogy	Chemistry, Geology	R
Mining engineering	Engineering, Geology	NR - Branch of mineralogy
Oceanography	Geology	R
Paleontology	Biology, Geology	R
Petroleum engineering	Engineering, Geology	R
Petrology	Geology	R
Remote sensing	Geography, Geology	R
Seismology	Geology	NR - Branch of earth science
Soil science	Environmental science, Geology	R

Although most child concepts are relevant, these results raise some questions about how OpenAlex determines which Level a concept should be. It should be noted that the concept 'Paleontology', which falls under 'Geology', but 'Archaeology' does not.

Next, we chose to explore the Level 2 concepts under Level 1 'Petrology' as one of our group members had previous experience in this field. Petrology is the study of rocks (igneous, metamorphic, and sedimentary) and the processes that form them. Table 11 shows the results of the evaluation of relevance.

Table 11
Level 2 Concepts under Level 1 Petrology

Concept	Parent Concept(s)	Relevance
Recrystallization (geology)	Paleontology, Petrology	R
Shear (geology)	Composite material, Paleontology, Petrology	NR - Related to structural geology
Provenance	Geochemistry, Paleontology, Petrology	R
Plasticine	Petrology	R
Sill	Geochemistry, Petrology, Structural engineering	R
Thin section	Geochemistry, Mineralogy, Petrology	R
Pothole (geology)	Geochemistry, Geomorphology, Petrology	R
Country rock	Geochemistry, Paleontology, Petrology	R
Metamorphism	Geochemistry, Paleontology, Petrology	R
Dike	Geochemistry, Paleontology, Petrology	R
Shield	Paleontology, Petrology	R
Seismic attribute	Geophysics, Petrology, Seismology	R
Caprock	Geotechnical engineering, Petroleum engineering, Petrology	R
Metamorphic rock	Geochemistry, Paleontology, Petrology	R
Horse	Paleontology, Petrology	NR - Related to mining engineering
Striation	Composite material, Paleontology, Petrology	R
Lithology	Geochemistry, Paleontology, Petrology	NR - Is a separate science
Mafic	Geochemistry, Paleontology, Petrology	NR - Is a type of igneous rock

These results demonstrate other issues as more detail is provided on the concepts. 'Recrystallization (geology)' refers to a chemical process where the atoms of a metamorphic rock are reorganized. When we look at this term's parent concepts, it is related to 'Petrology', though it is not related to 'Paleontology'; one could argue that 'Mineralogy' or 'Geochemistry' would be a much more appropriate parent.

This introduces one of the main issues with the 'Geology' hierarchy, that of 'Paleontology', which although is a very specific science related to the study of past life through fossils, has been incorrectly assigned as a parent term to 10 of the above 18 concepts, despite having no relevance to these terms at all. Yes, fossils may be contained within rocks, but that does not mean every rock-based concept should have 'Paleontology' as a parent.

As well, we also see some gaps in the concepts at this level. Although 'Metamorphic rock' has been included, neither 'Igneous rock' (Level 2) nor 'Sedimentary rock' (Level 2) are, despite being existing concepts. We believe this oversight is due to the latter two concepts having only parents 'Geochemistry' and 'Paleontology', but not 'Petrology', despite 'Paleontology' not being relevant to any of the three.

'Lithology' is the description of the physical properties of a rock. There is some minor overlap, however most professionals in the geology field agree that this is a separate science that complements 'Petrology', but is not a part of it. Considering this assessment, 'Lithology' should likely be a Level 1 concept, not Level 2.

Another example is 'Mafic', which should be a Level 3 concept with the Level 2 parent concept 'Igneous rock' as it is a specific type of igneous rock and not directly related to 'Petrology'.

For Level 2, we chose to explore the concept of 'Crude oil' as shown in Table 12.

Table 12

Level 3 Concepts under Level 2 Crude Oil

Concept	Parent Concept(s)	Relevance
Brent crude	Crude oil, Futures contract, Oil price, Volatility (finance)	R
Crack spread	Crude oil, Oil price	R
Demulsifier	Crude oil, Emulsion	R
Oil-storage trade	Crude oil, Oil price	R
West Texas intermediate	Crude oil, Futures contract, Oil price, Volatility (finance)	R

Under the Level 2 concept of 'Crude oil', we can see that it has a high degree of relevance. However, even though the classification is accurate, the list is far away from being exhaustive. For example, there are many crude oil products such as the Arabian light and the kurkuk that do not appear as child concepts.

For Level 3 we chose to look at 'Volcanic rock'; the results are shown in Table 13.

Table 13

Level 4 Concepts under Level 3 Volcanic Rock

Concept	Parent Concept(s)	Relevance
Haloferax volcanii	Archaea, Halophile	R
Shield volcano	Lava, Volcanism	R
Stratovolcano	Lava, Pyroclastic rock, Volcanic rock	R
Volcanic arc	Subduction	R
Volcanic belt	Volcanic rock	R
Volcanic cone	Lava, Pyroclastic rock, Volcanic rock, Volcanism	R
Volcanic glass	Volcanic rock	R
Volcanic plateau	Lava, Volcanic rock, Volcanism	R

Under the Level 3 concept of 'Volcanic rock' we can see a very similar trend to Level 2 concepts. There is a high degree of relevance, however the list of concepts is far from exhaustive.

Based on the results of evaluating the relevance of Levels 0 to 4, we can see that the relevance increases as we descend further into the levels. Levels 0 and 1 have multiple concepts that were evaluated as being not relevant, but the concepts at levels 2 and 3 were all evaluated as being relevant. However, we did remark that while all of the concepts were relevant there appeared to be significant gaps resulting in an incomplete list of concepts.

At Level 4, we looked for some geologically related concepts with children and chose to evaluate 'Engineering geology' and 'Andesite'. Tables 14 and 15 below show the results of the evaluation.

Table 14*Level 5 Concepts under Level 4 Engineering geology*

Concept	Parent Concept(s)	Relevance
Geobiology	Engineering geology, Regional geology	NR - not about engineering
Gemology	Engineering geology	NR - is a branch of mineralogy
Igneous petrology	Engineering geology	NR - is a branch of petrology

Table 15*Level 5 Concepts under Level 4 Andesite*

Concept	Parent Concept(s)	Relevance
Andesites	Andesite	R
Basaltic andesite	Andesite, Rhyolite	R
Dacite	Andesite, Rhyolite	R

The Level 4 concept 'Engineering geology' raises some concerns. First, it's defined as the application of the geologic sciences to engineering practice, which is quite broad. Technically, Level 1 concepts such as 'Geotechnical engineering', 'Mining engineering' and 'Petroleum engineering' could fall under this concept. The second concern is related to all three of the child terms, which should not be Level 5 concepts. 'Geobiology' should be a Level 1 concept, comparable to 'Geochemistry' or 'Geophysics'. 'Gemology' is a branch of mineralogy, and thus should be a Level 2 concept with Level 1 'Mineralogy' as its parent term. The existence of 'Igneous petrology' is interesting, however it also draws attention to more problems, such as the lack of a 'Sedimentary petrology' concept altogether. 'Metamorphic petrology' does exist as a Level 3 concept, though it has parents 'Hydrogeology' and 'Tectonics'. The Level 5 'Igneous petrology' should also be a Level 3 concept and a Level 3 'Sedimentary petrology' should be created, however all three of these concepts should have Level 2 'Petrology' as their parent, not 'Hydrogeology' or 'Tectonics'.

By comparison, the Level 4 concept 'Andesite' shows very different results. All three child concepts are relevant and have suitable parents. This demonstrates that although some concepts at Level 5 are relevant, there are significant issues within the hierarchy that need to be addressed to ensure that the nuance and complexity of the field is not lost due to OpenAlex misunderstanding the relationships between concepts.

We can conclude that the classification system is very complicated and while it is relevant, it is incomplete. Evaluating its relevance and exhaustivity was made simpler by being able to compare it to an exhaustive, fixed, non-subjective reference.

3.2 Evaluation of Indexing

The intent of this indexing analysis is to determine whether the documents are well-represented by the assigned OpenAlex concepts and evaluate the suitability of those terms.

3.2.1 Methodology

3.2.1.1 Article and Concept Selection

To initiate our evaluation, it was decided that a certain number of papers should be sampled for analysis. That number could not be finalized until all levels were explored to find a branch within the Level 0 Geology hierarchy that had terms extending down to Level 5. The process for selecting an appropriate level was partially combined with the exploration of the preceding level.

Using the OpenAlex alpha (OpenAlex, n.d.), we started by first filtering the works by the concept 'Geology'. The number of works counted was 13,906,157, which were sorted by 'most cited'. The first article selected for analysis was the top most cited article. Since it was apparent by the title that the paper was not about geology and considering that OpenAlex was only 7.6% confident about its indexing of the concept, we then searched through the API to find an article with the 'Geology' concept listed within the top three (most confident) concepts. The second article selected for analysis was the seventh most cited article in this search, it had the concept 'Mantle (geology)' as its third most confident concept and 'Geology' as its fourth.

We then selected the concept 'Geotechnical Engineering' for the Level 1 filter term. This concept was selected as it had the highest number of Level 2 children terms and some of our group members were already familiar with the engineering discipline. The number of works counted was 2,623,718, which were also sorted by 'most cited'. The third article selected for analysis was the top most cited work under 'Geotechnical Engineering' and was also the third most cited work under the Level 0 'Geology' search.

To determine the Level 2, Level 3, Level 4, and Level 5 terms, a series of searches were conducted using Huma Zafar's OpenAlex UI (Zafar, 2023). First we navigated to the Level 2 concept page, then searched for all Level 2 concepts that listed 'Geotechnical Engineering' as a parent term (n=118). Concepts selected for further exploration were those with five or more Level 3 children terms as it was anticipated that subsequent levels would have a higher likelihood of multiple children terms. Level 2 concepts assessed included 'Porosity' (20 children), 'Fracture (geology)' (8), 'Compaction' (5), 'Groundwater' (15), 'Water content' (15), 'Submarine pipeline' (5), and 'Landslide' (12). To narrow down the Level 2 concept options, a similar process was conducted; we navigated to the Level 3 concept page of Zafar's UI, then searched for all Level 3 concepts that had 'Porosity', 'Groundwater', 'Water content', or 'Landslide' listed as a parent concept, as well as had one or more children concepts. The results of this search are presented in Table 16.

Table 16
Assessment for Potential Level 2 and Level 3 Concepts

Level 2 Parent Concept	Level 3 Concepts with Children	# of Children	Times Parent Concept Mentioned in Children Concepts
Porosity	Metal foam	1	-
Porosity	Porous medium	6	-
Groundwater	Coal mining	12	1
Groundwater	Environmental remediation	10	2
Groundwater	Water table	3	-
Groundwater	Vadose zone	1	-
Groundwater	Subsidence	3	1
Groundwater	Aquifer	16	-
Groundwater	Meteoric water	1	-

Water Content	Wood drying	1	-
Water Content	Field capacity	2	-
Landslide	Landslide classification	1	-

Only four Level 3 concepts had five or more children concepts, three of those falling under Level 2 concept 'Groundwater' and one under 'Porosity'. The process was then repeated by searching for parent concepts 'Porous medium', 'Coal mining', 'Environmental remediation', and 'Aquifer', remarking that only 'Aquifer' had Level 4 concepts with children. These results are presented in Table 17.

Table 17
Assessment for Level 4 and Level 5 Concepts

Level 3 Parent Concept	Level 4 Concepts	# of Children	Level 5 Children Concept(s)	Parent Concept
Porous medium	Capillary pressure	-	-	Porosity
Porous medium	Poromechanics	-	-	
Porous medium	Darcy's law	-	-	
Porous medium	Darcy-Weisbach equation	-	-	
Porous medium	Viscous fingering	-	-	
Porous medium	Micromodel	-	-	
Coal mining	Coalbed methane	-	-	Groundwater
Coal mining	Underground coal gasification	-	-	
Coal mining	Surface mining	-	-	
Coal mining	Problems in coal mining	-	-	
Coal mining	Rock burst	-	-	
Coal mining	Enhanced coal bed methane recovery	-	-	
Coal mining	Coal basin	-	-	
Coal mining	Coal field	-	-	
Coal mining	Longwall mining	-	-	
Coal mining	Groundwater-related subsidence	-	-	
Coal mining	Mine safety	-	-	
Coal mining	Underground mining (soft rock)	-	-	
Environmental remediation	Soil vapor extraction	-	-	
Environmental remediation	Air sparging	-	-	
Environmental remediation	Total petroleum hydrocarbon	-	-	
Environmental remediation	Contaminated groundwater	-	-	
Environmental remediation	Permeable reactive barrier	-	-	
Environmental remediation	Electrokinetic remediation	-	-	
Environmental remediation	Groundwater remediation	-	-	
Environmental remediation	Contaminated land	-	-	
Environmental remediation	Remedial Action	-	-	
Environmental remediation	Soil remediation	-	-	
Aquifer	Artesian aquifer	1	Cone of depression	Groundwater
Aquifer	Piezometer	-	-	
Aquifer	Seawater intrusion	-	-	

Aquifer	Groundwater recharge	10	Groundwater model, Groundwater discharge, Aquifer properties, Aquifer test, Environmental isotopes, Surficial aquifer, Cone of depression, MODFLOW, Depression-focused recharge, Specific storage
Aquifer	Phreatic	-	-
Aquifer	Slug test	-	-
Aquifer	Submarine groundwater discharge	-	-
Aquifer	Groundwater flow	6	Groundwater model, Groundwater discharge, Cone of depression, MODFLOW, Depression-focused recharge, Groundwater flow equation
Aquifer	Saltwater intrusion	-	-
Aquifer	Vertical electrical sounding	-	-
Aquifer	Conjunctive use	-	-
Aquifer	Capillary fringe	-	-
Aquifer	Groundwater pollution	-	-
Aquifer	Groundwater contamination	-	-
Aquifer	Drawdown (hydrology)	-	-
Aquifer	Groundwater resources	-	-

Following this assessment, 'Groundwater' was determined as the Level 2 concept with 'Aquifer' as the Level 3 concept. This process was then completed a final time at Level 5 using all three concepts that listed 'Aquifer' as a parent and had children concepts: 'Artesian aquifer', 'Groundwater flow', and 'Groundwater recharge'. However, rather than observing the number of children concepts, we kept track of how many of the three Level 4 parent concepts were listed. The results of this search are presented in Table 18, a total of eleven Level 5 concepts. The five Level 5 concepts selected as search terms were 'Cone of depression', 'Groundwater model', 'Groundwater discharge', 'MODFLOW', and 'Depression-focused recharge'.

Table 18
Assessment of Level 5 Concepts

Level 5 Concept	# of Parents	Level 4 Parent Concepts
Cone of depression	3	Artesian aquifer, Groundwater recharge, Groundwater flow
Groundwater model	2	Groundwater recharge, Groundwater flow
Groundwater discharge	2	Groundwater recharge, Groundwater flow
Aquifer properties	1	Groundwater recharge
Aquifer test	1	Groundwater recharge
Environmental isotopes	1	Groundwater recharge
Surficial aquifer	1	Groundwater recharge
MODFLOW	2	Groundwater recharge, Groundwater flow
Depression-focused recharge	2	Groundwater recharge, Groundwater flow
Specific storage	1	Groundwater recharge
Groundwater flow equation	1	Groundwater flow

Once the concept(s) for each level had been selected, we returned to sampling papers for analysis. We filtered the works on OpenAlex by Level 2 concept 'Groundwater', then using the same method mentioned above for the previous levels, searched the API for articles that listed 'Groundwater' in the top three most confident concepts. The search returned 314,638 articles, the top most cited and third most cited works becoming our fourth and fifth articles for analysis. We then filtered by Level 3 concept 'Aquifer', returning 168,234 works. Following the same API search method above, the top most cited and sixth most cited articles were selected as the sixth and seventh for analysis as they contained 'Aquifer' in their top three (most confident) concepts.

At Level 4, four separate searches were conducted; one for 'Artesian aquifer' (returned 4,553 works), one for 'Groundwater flow' (27,116 works), and one for 'Groundwater recharge' (45,915 works), then a combined search for all three (67,162 works). The same search process was conducted for the Level 5 concepts 'Cone of depression' (1,023 works), 'Groundwater model' (7,572 works), 'Groundwater discharge' (4,138 works), 'MODFLOW' (4,094 works), 'Depression-focused recharge' (4,084 works), as well as a combined search of all five concepts (16,286 works).

Some of the top most cited works returned in these searches were articles already selected for analysis, while many were also within the top ten most cited articles for multiple of the Level 4 and Level 5 searches. The remaining seven articles selected for analysis were found within these searches and details on which searches they appeared in are presented in Appendix A.

3.2.1.2 Article Analysis Process

Following our exploration of OpenAlex, a total of fourteen works were selected for further analysis from within the Level 0 'Geology' hierarchy. An indexing analysis exercise was prepared that imitated Assignments 1 and 2 for this class, ISI 5302. The fourteen articles were split into two sets of seven, then each set of articles was assigned to two of our group members. The sets were determined by assessing the total number of concepts indexed by OpenAlex for each work, then attempting to sort them by perceived topic (ex. engineering articles grouped together and aquatic environment grouped together) while also aiming to have the same total number of concepts allocated to the group members.

The first part of the analysis was an indexing exercise completed by the group members. Each person was to review the articles assigned to them and then propose indexing terms for that article. Group members were also asked to verify if the indexing term they wanted to use exists in OpenAlex as a concept.

The second part of the analysis exercise was an assessment of OpenAlex's indexing. Group members were asked to review the list of concepts OpenAlex had indexed to each article they had previously read and determine if the term was a suitable concept for the paper. As well, group members were asked to indicate on an overall scale whether or not they considered the paper to be about our Level 0 concept, 'Geology'.

3.2.2 Results

3.2.2.1 Suitability of OpenAlex Assigned Concepts

From a simple perspective, the OpenAlex concepts do represent the articles indexed. Between all fourteen works sampled, a total of 232 concepts were indexed, which our group determined were approximately 60% correct. 140 concepts were appropriately assigned to articles, while 92 were not. The full details of the concepts evaluated and decisions made by each group member for each article are presented in Appendix B, which also includes OpenAlex's confidence scores. If we instead assess the concepts' while looking at suitability of terms with 0.50 confidence or higher (as well as 0.50 and lower), there is a marked improvement in overall accuracy as seen in Table 19. The accuracy for all fourteen articles increases by 7% at minimum, up to 38% at best, with an average overall improvement of 23%.

Table 19

Suitability of Assigned OpenAlex Concepts, by Article, by Confidence Score

Article #	Total # of Concepts	All Concepts		Confidence Above 0.50			Confidence Below 0.50		
		# Suitable (%)		# of Concepts	# Suitable (%)		# of Concepts	# Suitable (%)	
1	21	7	33.3%	7	5	71.4%	14	2	14.3%
2	16	9	56.3%	5	4	80.0%	11	5	45.5%
3	18	9	50.0%	5	4	80.0%	13	5	38.5%
4	18	13	72.2%	9	9	100%	9	4	44.4%
5	10	6	60.0%	2	2	100%	8	4	50.0%
6	22	16	72.7%	9	8	88.9%	13	8	61.5%
7	17	7	41.2%	4	2	50%	13	5	38.5%
8	21	11	52.4%	8	8	100%	13	3	23.1%
9	14	13	92.7%	2	2	100%	12	11	91.7%
10	18	12	66.7%	6	5	83.3%	12	7	58.3%
11	13	12	92.3%	7	7	100%	6	5	83.3%
12	14	7	50.0%	5	4	80.0%	9	3	33.3%
13	16	11	68.9%	7	5	71.4%	9	6	66.7%
14	14	7	50.0%	5	4	80.0%	9	3	33.3%
All	232	140	61.3%	81	69	84.6%	219	71	48.7%

Since it was determined that some articles were not about 'Geology', we also thought to see if there was any change if these articles were excluded from the calculations, however excluding articles #1, #4, and #10 did not have any discernible impact on the above observations.

A similar thought was had regarding article #7, which had the lowest score of 50% when analyzing concepts with confidence scores above 0.50. When removed from the dataset, there is a small increase of ~1% to the all article scores. It is noted that the main discrepancy between article #7 and the assigned OpenAlex concepts is due to the human-indexed term 'Dispersivity'. This term is related to groundwater and geology, however does not exist in OpenAlex. OpenAlex does have the concept 'Dispersion (optics)' and has indexed it as its second most confident (0.5393159) concept, as well as associated concepts 'Optics', 'Physics', 'Power (physics)', and 'Quantum mechanics'. This raises one of the issues of OpenAlex, particularly as it relates to topical headings with subdivisions and homonyms; once a term has been assigned as a concept, OpenAlex does not appear to index the term a second time. Although the '(optics)' facet is added to the Level 2 concept 'Dispersion' within Level 1 hierarchy 'Optics', a 'Dispersion' concept with the facet 'Geotechnical engineering' or 'Hydrogeology' is not created.

This issue also occurs with article #10, which includes two multi-facet concepts; 'Hydrology (agriculture)' and 'Vegetation (pathology)'. 'Vegetation (pathology)' is the exact same problem as above, the concept 'Vegetation (ecology)' has not been created. For

'Hydrology (agriculture)', which is a child concept of 'Geotechnical engineering', the issue is related to the added facet. The Level 2 concept 'Agriculture' has parents 'Archaeology' and 'Ecology', neither of which are regularly associated with 'Geology' nor 'Geotechnical engineering'. As well, this implies that hydrology is only about water availability and its impact on human activity as it relates to farming. There should be a second 'Hydrology' concept with the appropriate parent facet that refers to the study of water distribution and movement on and below earth's surface. This issue could potentially be resolved by removing the facet altogether, however there will then be more crossovers with unrelated concepts.

Similar issues can be seen in the concept suitability assessment of the other articles (Appendix B) and are typically related to Level 0, Level 1, and Level 2 concepts that have existing homonyms in other disciplines. These results prompted us to assess the accuracy of the concepts by level, as detailed in Appendix C. The consolidated results of all fourteen articles are presented in Table 20. We can see that the assigned concepts range in accuracy by level, with Level 0 and Level 1 concepts having 48% suitability, while Level 5 concepts are 87.5% suitable. However, only eight Level 5 concepts were assigned across all fourteen articles (3.5% of all concepts), whereas Levels 0 and 1 totalled 112 (48.3% of all concepts). These results suggest that OpenAlex should focus on indexing concepts at Levels 2-5, and only include Level 0 or 1 concepts if the confidence score is above 0.50.

Table 20

Suitability of Assigned OpenAlex Concepts, by Level, Across All 14 Articles

Concept Level	Total # of Concepts	% of All Concepts	# Suitable (%)		# Unsuitable (%)	
0	52	22.41%	25	48.08%	27	51.92%
1	60	25.86%	29	48.33%	31	51.67%
2	77	33.19%	54	70.13%	23	29.87%
3	23	9.91%	16	69.57%	7	30.43%
4	12	5.17%	9	75.00%	3	25.00%
5	8	3.45%	7	87.50%	1	12.50%
All Levels	232	100.00%	140	60.34%	92	39.66%

3.2.2.2 Comparison Between Group Member and AI Indexing

The assessment of OpenAlex's indexed concepts led into our analysis of the group members' indexed terms. Considering that nearly 40% of the AI-indexed concepts were not suitable, we then searched through our indexed terms to determine if there are any concepts that exist and could have been used, as well as if there are any terms that do not exist but potentially should. Table 21 includes a summarized version of the detailed analysis presented in Appendix D. Our group members found 61 existing OpenAlex concepts that could have been used across the fourteen articles in place of the 92 we determined were not suitable.

As well, we also determined 27 terms that are not OpenAlex concepts but both group members indexed as a key concept of the article. Most of these terms were distinct to the articles they were indexed from and in our opinion would likely be Level 4 or Level 5 (or even Level 6) concepts if included in OpenAlex.

Table 21*Comparison of Group Members vs. OpenAlex Indexing*

Article #	Group Member Indexing			OpenAlex Assigned Concepts					
	Unique Index Terms	OA Concepts Indexed	Unused Concepts	# of OA Concepts	Suitable OA Concepts	Unsuitable			
1	32	8	25.0%	6	21	7	33.3%	14	66.7%
2	22	12	54.5%	7	16	9	56.3%	7	43.7%
3	20	12	60.0%	5	18	9	50.0%	9	50.0%
4	21	9	42.9%	4	18	13	72.2%	5	27.8%
5	13	5	38.5%	2	10	4	60.0%	6	40.0%
6	30	9	30.0%	2	22	16	72.7%	6	27.3%
7	19	9	47.4%	4	17	7	41.2%	10	58.8%
8	26	12	46.2%	4	21	11	52.4%	10	47.6%
9	18	7	38.9%	3	14	13	92.9%	1	7.1%
10	24	11	45.8%	5	18	12	66.7%	6	33.3%
11	16	10	62.5%	5	13	12	92.3%	1	7.7%
12	20	10	50.0%	6	14	7	50.0%	7	50.0%
13	22	6	27.3%	1	16	11	68.8%	5	31.2%
14	21	9	42.9%	7	14	7	50.0%	7	50.0%
All	304	129	42.4%	61	232	140	60.3%	92	39.7%

4 Conclusion

Although OpenAlex is a great resource for locating works that may not be included within other paid and non-paid indexes, there are still numerous issues with the concept hierarchies that should be resolved in order for the tool to reach its full potential.

There are many Level 1 (and 2) concepts that could be included at Level 0 (ex. Ecology, Hydrology, Hydrogeology, Geochemistry, etc.) that would resolve issues with homonymy and articles being indexed within two non-related disciplines (ex. Computer science and Geology, or Pathology and Ecology, etc.). As well, these issues surrounding homonymy have resulted in significant gaps in the parent-child relationship, as many concepts do not have a parent term at all due to their lack of creation. By resolving this issue, these voids could be filled, thus reestablishing a proper hierarchy.

This adjustment could also help with issues surrounding exhaustivity, since many of the terms our group indexed that do not yet exist as concepts would likely be Level 5 or 6. By increasing the number of Level 0 terms, the entire hierarchy would shift, allowing for more detailed and specific concepts at the lower levels, including terms that may only be relevant to certain works.

An assessment of certain Level 4 and 5 terms is also required to determine if OpenAlex has correctly located them within the concept hierarchy, as there are a number of geology related concepts incorrectly identified as Level 5 when they should be Level 1 or 2, resulting in significant impacts to associated children concepts and gaps in the hierarchy. As a related suggestion, certain Level 1 concepts need to be reassessed in terms of parent-child relationships. For example, 'Paleontology' has 637 children, the majority of which are not relevant.

Although these recommendations are specific to the Level 0 'Geology', it is assumed that the issues discussed in this report are relevant to all Level 0 concepts and the OpenAlex hierarchies overall. We anticipate that by addressing certain concerns, such as the omission of facet-specific concepts due to another already having been created, issues surrounding homonymy and parent-child relationships will be vastly improved across the entire database.

Until these problems can be addressed, OpenAlex should focus on indexing concepts at Levels 2 through 5, since they are statistically more suitable for the articles they are assigned to when compared to concepts at Levels 0 and 1.

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Appendix A - List of Articles Sampled for Indexing Analysis

#	Article	Concepts Search (Level)	Citations
1	Szegedy, C. et al. (2015). Going deeper with convolutions. <i>2015 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)</i> , 1-9. IEEE. https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2015.7298594	Geology (0)	#1 most cited
2	Sun, S. -s., & McDonough, W. F. (1989). Chemical and isotopic systematics of oceanic basalts: implications for mantle composition and processes. <i>Geological Society</i> , 42(1), 313–345. Geological Society of London. https://doi.org/10.1144/gsl.sp.1989.042.01.19	Geology (0)	#7 most cited
3	van Genuchten, M. Th. (1980). A Closed-form Equation for Predicting the Hydraulic Conductivity of Unsaturated Soils. <i>Soil Science Society of America Journal</i> , 44(5), 892–898. Wiley. https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1980.03615995004400050002x	Geotechnical Engineering (1) Geology (0)	#1 most cited #3 most cited
4	Luo, Y. et al. (2014). A review on the occurrence of micropollutants in the aquatic environment and their fate and removal during wastewater treatment. <i>Science of The Total Environment</i> , 473–474, 619–641. Elsevier. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.12.065	Groundwater (2)	#1 most cited
5	Appelo, C. A. J., & Postma, D. (2004). <i>Geochemistry, Groundwater and Pollution</i> (2nd ed.). CRC Press. https://doi.org/10.1201/9781439833544	Groundwater (2)	#3 most cited
6	Heberer, T. (2002). Occurrence, fate, and removal of pharmaceutical residues in the aquatic environment: a review of recent research data. <i>Toxicology Letters</i> , 131(1–2), 5–17. Elsevier. https://doi.org/10.1016/s0378-4274(02)00041-3	Aquifer (3) Groundwater recharge (5) Combined Search (4)	#1 most cited #1 most cited #6 most cited
7	Gelhar, L. W., Welty, C., & Rehfeldt, K. R. (1992). A critical review of data on field-scale dispersion in aquifers. <i>Water Resources Research</i> , 28(7), 1955–1974. American Geophysical Union. https://doi.org/10.1029/92wr00607	Aquifer (3)	#6 most cited
8	Bouwer, H., & Rice, R. C. (1976). A slug test for determining hydraulic conductivity of unconfined aquifers with completely or partially penetrating wells. <i>Water Resources Research</i> , 12(3), 423–428. American Geophysical Union. https://doi.org/10.1029/wr012i003p00423	Artesian aquifer (4) Cone of depression (5) Combined Search (5)	#1 most cited #1 most cited #5 most cited
9	Harbaugh, A. W. et al. (2000). MODFLOW-2000, The U.S. Geological Survey modular ground-water model: User guide to modularization concepts and the ground-water flow process. <i>Open-File Report</i> . US Geological Survey. https://doi.org/10.3133/ofr200092	Groundwater flow (4) MODFLOW (5) Combined Search (5) Combined Search (4)	#1 most cited #1 most cited #1 most cited #3 most cited
10	Zhang, L., Dawes, W. R., & Walker, G. R. (2001). Response of mean annual evapotranspiration to vegetation changes at catchment scale. <i>Water Resources Research</i> , 37(3), 701–708. American Geophysical Union. https://doi.org/10.1029/2000wr900325	Combined Search (4) Groundwater recharge (4)	#2 most cited #2 most cited
11	Wada, Y. et al. (2010). Global depletion of groundwater resources. <i>Geophysical Research Letters</i> , 37(20). American Geophysical Union. https://doi.org/10.1029/2010gl044571	Depression-focused recharge (5) Combined Search (5) Groundwater recharge (4) Combined Search (4)	#1 most cited #2 most cited #4 most cited #5 most cited
12	Tóth, J. (1963). A theoretical analysis of groundwater flow in small drainage basins. <i>Journal of Geophysical Research</i> , 68(16), 4795–4812. American Geophysical Union. https://doi.org/10.1029/jz068i016p04795	Groundwater model (5) Combined Search (5) Combined Search (4)	#1 most cited #4 most cited #7 most cited
13	Moore, W. S. (1996). Large groundwater inputs to coastal waters revealed by 226Ra enrichments. <i>Nature</i> , 380(6575), 612–614. Springer Science and Business Media LLC. https://doi.org/10.1038/380612a0	Groundwater discharge (5) Combined Search (5)	#1 most cited #6 most cited
14	Scanlon, B. R., Healy, R. W., & Cook, P. G. (2002). Choosing appropriate techniques for quantifying groundwater recharge. <i>Hydrogeology Journal</i> , 10(1), 18–39. Springer Science and Business Media LLC. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10040-001-0176-2	Depression-focused recharge (5) Combined Search (5)	#2 most cited #3 most cited

Appendix B - Suitability of Assigned OpenAlex Concepts

Article #	OpenAlex Assigned Concepts	Confidence	Level	Suitable Concept?		Final Decision	Accuracy	Classification under Geology
				M1	M2			
1	Computer Science	0.7915665	0	No	Yes	Yes	71.43% (5 of 7 concepts above 0.5 confidence)	Incorrect The article is about computer science and convolutional neural networks. No reference to any geological principles.
	Architecture	0.6833388	2	No	No	No		
	Convolutional neural network	0.6629484	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Intuition	0.62789375	2	No	No	No		
	Artificial Intelligence	0.6063455	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Deep learning	0.53559685	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Network architecture	0.5039336	2	No	Yes	Yes		
	Context (archaeology)	0.48349598	2	No	No	No	14.29% (2 of 14 concepts under 0.5 confidence)	
	Artificial neural network	0.4429452	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Scale (ratio)	0.43330717	2	No	No	No		
	Pattern recognition (psychology)	0.3848013	2	No	Yes	No		
	Machine learning	0.35951412	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Computer network	0.08953968	1	No	Yes	No		
	Geology	0.075799584	0	No	No	No		
	Art	0	0	No	No	No		
	Paleontology	0	1	No	No	No		
	Philosophy	0	0	No	No	No		
	Physics	0	0	No	No	No		
	Epistemology	0	1	No	No	No		
	Quantum mechanics	0	1	No	No	No		
	Visual arts	0	1	No	No	No		
						33.33% (7 of 21)	Total	
2	Systematics	0.8269634	3	No	No	No	80% (4 of 5)	Correct
	Basalt	0.79162747	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Mantle (geology)	0.74632263	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Geology	0.6691242	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Geochemistry	0.5724987	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Oceanic crust	0.41591695	4	No	Yes	Yes	45.45% (5 of 11)	
	Earth science	0.41270584	1	Yes	No	Yes		
	Chemical composition	0.41162562	2	No	Yes	Yes		
	Subduction	0.298071	3	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Paleontology	0.22567448	1	No	No	No		
	Chemistry	0.121337146	0	No	Yes	No		
	Biology	0.062390447	0	No	No	No		
	Tectonics	0.045977205	2	No	Yes	Yes		
	Taxonomy (biology)	0	2	No	No	No		
	Botany	0	1	No	No	No		
	Organic chemistry	0	1	No	Yes	No		
						56.25% (9 of 16)	Total	

3	Hydraulic conductivity	0.8961098	3	Yes	Yes	Yes	80.00% (4 of 5)	Correct
	Soil Water	0.7800027	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Conductivity	0.60378855	2	No	No	No		
	Pressure head	0.5543444	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Soil science	0.52514577	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Water retention	0.47506234	3	Yes	No	Yes	38.46% (5 of 13)	
	Range (aeronautics)	0.45120913	2	No	No	No		
	Water content	0.44140258	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Materials science	0.37461734	0	Yes	No	No		
	Mathematics	0.35397366	0	No	Yes	No		
	Geotechnical Engineering	0.3236606	1	Yes	No	Yes		
	Environmental Science	0.31797552	0	No	No	No		
	Thermodynamics	0.28150553	1	No	No	No		
	Chemistry	0.19706169	0	No	No	No		
	Geology	0.1966592	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Physics	0.15304697	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Composite material	0.057198822	1	No	No	No		
	Physical chemistry	0	1	No	No	No		
							50.00% (9 of 18)	
4	Effluent	0.7554006	2	Yes	Yes	Yes	100.00% (9 of 9)	Incorrect This article is related to environmental science and water treatment, however some geologically relevant concepts are used.
	Nanofiltration	0.74519706	3	Yes	No	Yes		
	Environmental Science	0.7057383	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Sewage treatment	0.6346572	2	Yes	No	Yes		
	Wastewater	0.6187307	2	Yes	No	Yes		
	Surface water	0.6041362	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Sewage	0.5598123	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Environmental chemistry	0.5136363	1	Yes	No	Yes		
	Groundwater	0.50842637	2	Yes	No	Yes		
	Water treatment	0.49939895	2	Yes	Yes	Yes	44.44% (4 of 9)	
	Reverse osmosis	0.48816282	3	Yes	No	Yes		
	Water pollution	0.42573324	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Environmental engineering	0.3804386	1	Yes	No	Yes		
	Chemistry	0.26439786	0	Yes	No	No		
	Membrane	0.08337873	2	Yes	No	No		
	Biochemistry	0	1	Yes	No	No		
	Geotechnical Engineering	0	1	No	Yes	No		
	Engineering	0	0	Yes	No	No		
							72.22% (13 of 18)	
5	Groundwater	0.70394653	2	Yes	Yes	Yes	100.00% (2 of 2)	Correct
	Pollution	0.6168504	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Geology	0.49932265	0	Yes	Yes	Yes	50.00% (4 of 8)	
	Geochemistry	0.4715935	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Environmental Science	0.42574465	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		

	Water resource management	0.38119146	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Mining engineering	0.33733338	1	No	Yes	No		
	Geotechnical Engineering	0.054259658	1	No	Yes	No		
	Ecology	0	1	No	No	No		
	Biology	0	0	No	No	No		
				Total			60.00% (6 of 10)	
6	Effluent	0.73333883	2	Yes	Yes	Yes	88.89% (8 of 9)	Correct
	Environmental chemistry	0.67426586	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Clofibric acid	0.6519887	2	Yes	No	No		
	Aquatic environment	0.6020979	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Surface water	0.59900534	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Sewage	0.564487	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Groundwater	0.5380369	2	Yes	No	Yes		
	Environmental science	0.5378159	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Leachate	0.5110568	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Groundwater recharge	0.4565709	4	Yes	No	No	61.54% (8 of 13)	
	Contamination	0.44535473	2	Yes	No	Yes		
	Subsoil	0.4358312	3	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Chemistry	0.27806056	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Environmental engineering	0.2237421	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Biology	0.1205599	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Ecology	0.10727188	1	Yes	No	Yes		
	Aquifer	0.092891395	3	Yes	No	No		
	Biochemistry	0	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Geotechnical Engineering	0	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Soil water	0	2	Yes	No	No		
	Engineering	0	0	Yes	No	No		
	Soil science	0	1	Yes	No	No		
				Total			72.73% (16 of 22)	
7	Aquifer	0.68146455	3	Yes	Yes	Yes	50.00% (2 of 4)	Correct
	Dispersion (optics)	0.5393159	2	No	No	No		
	Transverse plane	0.5223635	2	No	No	No		
	Scale (ratio)	0.51354027	2	No	Yes	Yes		
	Geotechnical Engineering	0.4210803	1	Yes	Yes	Yes	38.46% (5 of 13)	
	Reliability (semiconductor)	0.42028216	3	No	No	No		
	Geology	0.40158972	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Environmental science	0.3976636	0	No	No	No		
	Soil science	0.38834006	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Hydrology (agriculture)	0.3408016	2	No	No	No		
	Groundwater	0.23263228	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Physics	0.2069343	0	No	No	No		
	Engineering	0.16444868	0	No	Yes	Yes		
Optics	0.122540414	1	No	No	No			

	Power (physics)	0	2	No	No	No		
	Structural engineering	0	1	No	No	No		
	Quantum mechanics	0	1	No	No	No		
				Total			41.18% (7 of 17)	
8	Aquifer	0.9374456	3	Yes	Yes	Yes	100.00% (8 of 8)	Correct
	Slug test	0.90354455	4	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Hydraulic conductivity	0.82769346	3	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Geotechnical Engineering	0.64841783	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Geology	0.6467812	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Aquifer test	0.6251378	5	Yes	No	Yes		
	Specific storage	0.5919796	5	No	Yes	Yes		
	Hydraulic head	0.5029246	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Water table	0.48581624	3	Yes	Yes	Yes	23.08% (3 of 13)	
	RADIUS	0.4685313	2	No	No	No		
	Water well	0.450167	3	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Cone of depression	0.4293156	5	No	No	No		
	Mechanics	0.33430034	1	No	No	No		
	Soil science	0.33407265	1	No	Yes	No		
	Groundwater	0.30531877	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Artesian aquifer	0.24204537	4	No	No	No		
	Groundwater recharge	0.07935038	4	No	Yes	No		
	Soil water	0.07564294	2	No	Yes	No		
	Physics	0	0	No	No	No		
	Computer security	0	1	No	No	No		
	Computer science	0	0	No	No	No		
				Total			52.38% (11 of 21)	
9	MODFLOW	0.98670554	5	Yes	Yes	Yes	100.00% (2 of 2)	Correct
	Modular design	0.54395956	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Flow (mathematics)	0.4974821	2	Yes	Yes	Yes	91.67% (11 of 12)	
	Computer science	0.4974821	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Process (computing)	0.43942407	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Groundwater	0.41782606	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Applied mathematics	0.36431497	1	Yes	No	Yes		
	Groundwater flow	0.3022686	4	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Mathematics	0.26003385	0	Yes	No	Yes		
	Geotechnical Engineering	0.17389593	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Engineering	0.17170149	0	Yes	No	Yes		
	Programming language	0.15870166	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Geometry	0.110797435	1	Yes	No	No		
	Aquifer	0	3	Yes	Yes	Yes		
				Total			92.86% (13 of 14)	

10	Evapotranspiration	0.9594713	2	Yes	Yes	Yes	83.33% (5 of 6)	Incorrect Article is focused on environmental science and geography, though does mention some geological principles.
	Groundwater recharge	0.7830907	4	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Environmental science	0.73854846	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Hydrology (agriculture)	0.6946968	2	No	Yes	Yes		
	Water balance	0.68736136	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Vegetation (pathology)	0.54918003	2	No	No	No		
	Interception	0.46980366	2	No	Yes	Yes	58.33% (7 of 12)	
	Drainage basin	0.43149108	2	Yes	No	Yes		
	Groundwater	0.26782614	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Geography	0.11232215	0	No	Yes	Yes		
	Geology	0.09754935	0	Yes	No	Yes		
	Ecology	0.09673369	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Aquifer	0.073232144	3	No	No	No		
	Medicine	0	0	No	No	No		
	Geotechnical Engineering	0	1	Yes	No	Yes		
	Cartography	0	1	No	No	No		
	Pathology	0	1	No	No	No		
	Biology	0	0	Yes	No	No		
							Total	66.67% (12 of 18)
11	Groundwater recharge	0.9420371	4	Yes	Yes	Yes	100.00% (7 of 7)	Correct
	Groundwater	0.8467821	2	Yes	No	Yes		
	Overexploitation	0.7284096	2	Yes	No	Yes		
	Aquifer	0.66727173	3	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Hydrology (agriculture)	0.5902513	2	No	Yes	Yes		
	Environmental science	0.57548153	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Depression-focused recharge	0.5246299	5	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Surface runoff	0.49859548	2	Yes	No	Yes	83.33% (5 of 6)	
	Water resource management	0.39430025	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Geology	0.31112242	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Ecology	0.08655745	1	Yes	No	Yes		
	Geotechnical Engineering	0	1	No	Yes	Yes		
	Biology	0	0	No	No	No		
							Total	92.31% (12 of 13)
12	Geology	0.64428717	0	Yes	Yes	Yes	80.00% (4 of 5)	Correct
	Groundwater flow	0.6427249	4	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Groundwater	0.6283174	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Hydrology (agriculture)	0.5324149	2	No	No	No		
	Drainage	0.52212244	2	No	Yes	Yes		
	Groundwater model	0.49022967	5	No	Yes	Yes	33.33% (3 of 9)	
	Drainage basin	0.47290504	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Environmental science	0.40497985	0	No	No	No		
	Aquifer	0.28831482	3	No	No	No		
	Geotechnical Engineering	0.2403427	1	Yes	No	Yes		

	Geography	0.083657295	0	No	Yes	No		
	Ecology	0	1	No	No	No		
	Cartography	0	1	No	No	No		
	Biology	0	0	No	No	No		
				Total			50.00% (7 of 14)	
13	Brackish water	0.823701	3	Yes	Yes	Yes	71.43% (5 of 7)	Correct
	Groundwater	0.8024738	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Submarine groundwater discharge	0.7122134	4	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Environmental science	0.6847515	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Hydrology (agriculture)	0.5821396	2	No	No	No		
	Seawater	0.50797445	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Flux (metallurgy)	0.5058186	2	No	Yes	No		
	Groundwater discharge	0.49495047	5	Yes	Yes	Yes	66.67% (6 of 9)	
	Oceanography	0.48582244	1	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Groundwater flow	0.41743106	4	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Geology	0.27945563	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Aquifer	0.27386236	3	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Salinity	0.25561395	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Geotechnical Engineering	0	1	No	Yes	No		
	Materials science	0	0	No	No	No		
	Metallurgy	0	1	No	Yes	No		
				Total			68.88% (11 of 16)	
14	Groundwater recharge	0.9920201	4	Yes	Yes	Yes	80.00% (4 of 5)	Correct
	Hydrogeology	0.6032669	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Aquifer	0.5418715	3	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Hydrology (agriculture)	0.524074	2	No	No	No		
	Depression-focused recharge	0.5140025	5	No	Yes	Yes		
	Environmental science	0.45165053	0	No	No	No	33.33% (3 of 9)	
	Groundwater	0.43947458	2	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Reliability (semiconductor)	0.42420095	3	No	No	No		
	Vadose zone	0.4101715	3	No	No	No		
	Geology	0.2968312	0	Yes	Yes	Yes		
	Geotechnical Engineering	0.111534595	1	No	Yes	Yes		
	Power (physics)	0.08900833	2	No	No	No		
	Physics	0	0	No	No	No		
Quantum mechanics	0	1	No	No	No			
				Total			50.00% (7 of 14)	

Appendix C - Suitability of Assigned OpenAlex Concepts, by Level, By Article

Article #	Concept Level	# of Concepts	% of All Concepts	# Unsuitable (%)		# Suitable (%)	
1	0	5	23.81%	4	80.00%	1	20.00%
	1	7	33.33%	5	71.43%	2	28.57%
	2	9	42.86%	5	55.56%	4	44.44%
	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-
	All	21	100.00%	14	66.67%	7	33.33%
2	0	3	18.75%	2	66.67%	1	33.33%
	1	5	31.25%	3	60.00%	2	40.00%
	2	5	31.25%	1	20.00%	4	80.00%
	3	2	12.50%	1	50.00%	1	50.00%
	4	1	6.25%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-
	All	16	100.00%	7	43.75%	9	56.25%
3	0	6	33.33%	4	66.67%	2	33.33%
	1	5	27.78%	3	60.00%	2	40.00%
	2	5	27.78%	2	40.00%	3	60.00%
	3	2	11.11%	0	0.00%	2	100.00%
	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-
	All	18	100.00%	9	50.00%	9	50.00%
4	0	3	16.67%	2	66.67%	1	33.33%
	1	4	22.22%	2	50.00%	2	50.00%
	2	9	50.00%	1	11.11%	8	88.89%
	3	2	11.11%	0	0.00%	2	100.00%
	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-
	All	18	100.00%	5	27.78%	13	72.22%
5	0	3	30.00%	1	33.33%	2	66.67%
	1	5	50.00%	3	60.00%	2	40.00%
	2	2	20.00%	0	0.00%	2	100.00%
	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-
	All	10	100.00%	4	40.00%	6	60.00%
6	0	4	18.18%	1	25.00%	3	75.00%
	1	6	27.27%	1	16.67%	5	83.33%
	2	9	40.91%	2	22.22%	7	77.78%
	3	2	9.09%	1	50.00%	1	50.00%
	4	1	4.55%	1	100.00%	0	0.00%
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-
	All	22	100.00%	6	27.27%	16	72.73%
7	0	4	23.53%	2	50.00%	2	50.00%
	1	5	29.41%	3	60.00%	2	40.00%

	2	6	35.29%	4	66.67%	2	33.33%
	3	2	11.76%	1	50.00%	1	50.00%
	4	-	-	-	-	-	-
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-
	All	17	100.00%	10	58.82%	7	41.18%
8	0	3	14.29%	2	66.67%	1	33.33%
	1	4	19.05%	3	75.00%	1	25.00%
	2	4	19.05%	2	50.00%	2	50.00%
	3	4	19.05%	0	0.00%	4	100.00%
	4	3	14.29%	2	66.67%	1	33.33%
	5	3	14.29%	1	33.33%	2	66.67%
	All	21	100.00%	10	47.62%	11	52.38%
9	0	3	21.43%	0	0.00%	3	100.00%
	1	4	28.57%	1	25.00%	3	75.00%
	2	4	28.57%	0	0.00%	4	100.00%
	3	1	7.14%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	4	1	7.14%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	5	1	7.14%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	All	14	100.00%	1	7.14%	13	92.86%
10	0	5	27.78%	2	40.00%	3	60.00%
	1	4	22.22%	2	50.00%	2	50.00%
	2	7	38.89%	1	14.29%	6	85.71%
	3	1	5.56%	1	100.00%	0	0.00%
	4	1	5.56%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	5	-	-	-	-	-	-
	All	18	100.00%	6	33.33%	12	66.67%
11	0	3	23.08%	1	33.33%	2	66.67%
	1	3	23.08%	0	0.00%	3	100.00%
	2	4	30.77%	0	0.00%	4	100.00%
	3	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	4	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	5	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	All	13	100.00%	1	7.69%	12	92.31%
12	0	4	28.57%	3	75.00%	1	25.00%
	1	3	21.43%	2	66.67%	1	33.33%
	2	4	28.57%	1	25.00%	3	75.00%
	3	1	7.14%	1	100.00%	0	0.00%
	4	1	7.14%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	5	1	7.14%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	All	14	100.00%	7	50.00%	7	50.00%
13	0	3	18.75%	1	33.33%	2	66.67%
	1	3	18.75%	2	66.67%	1	33.33%
	2	5	31.25%	2	40.00%	3	60.00%
	3	2	12.50%	0	0.00%	2	100.00%
	4	2	12.50%	0	0.00%	2	100.00%
	5	1	6.25%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	All	16	100.00%	5	31.25%	11	68.75%

14	0	3	21.43%	2	66.67%	1	33.33%
	1	2	14.29%	1	50.00%	1	50.00%
	2	4	28.57%	2	50.00%	2	50.00%
	3	3	21.43%	2	66.67%	1	33.33%
	4	1	7.14%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	5	1	7.14%	0	0.00%	1	100.00%
	All	14	100.00%	7	50.00%	7	50.00%
All Articles	0	52	22.41%	27	51.92%	25	48.08%
	1	60	25.86%	31	51.67%	29	48.33%
	2	77	33.19%	23	29.87%	54	70.13%
	3	23	9.91%	7	30.43%	16	69.57%
	4	12	5.17%	3	25.00%	9	75.00%
	5	8	3.45%	1	12.50%	7	87.50%
	All	232	100.00%	92	39.66%	140	60.34%

Appendix D - Human vs. AI Indexing Comparison

*denotes term that both group members indexed

(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?	OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
1	ImageNet*	No	No	Computer Science	Visualization (2)
	Computing resources	No	No	Architecture	Computer vision (1)
	Resource allocation	No	No	Convolutional neural network	Hebbian theory (3)
	Network depth	No	No	Intuition	Objection detection (3)
	Visualization	Yes	No	Artificial Intelligence	Quality Assessment (3)
	Network Width	No	No	Deep learning	Computer architecture (1)
	Computer vision	Yes	No	Network architecture	Terms That Should Be Concepts
	Computational budget	No	No	Context (archaeology)	
	Neural net architecture	No	No	Artificial neural network	ImageNet*
	Quality optimization	No	No	Scale (ratio)	Hebbian principle*
	Hebbian theory	Yes	No	Pattern recognition (psychology)	Architectural decisions*
	Hebbian principle*	No	No	Machine learning	GoogLeNet*
	Classification	No	No	Computer network	Neural network*
	Image classification	No	No	Geology	Best OA Concepts
	Detection	No	No	Art	
	Object detection	Yes	No	Paleontology	Convolutional neural network (2)
	Objection classification	No	No	Philosophy	Deep learning (2)
	Quality assessment	Yes	No	Physics	
	Network utilization	No	No	Epistemology	
	Conventional network	No	No	Quantum mechanics	
	Architectural decisions*	No	No	Visual arts	
	Network layers	No	No	Total Concepts	
	Deep learning	Yes	Yes	21	
	GoogLeNet*	No	No	Total Suitable	
	Multi-scale processing	No	No	7	
	State of the Art	No	No	Unsuitable	
	ILSVRC14	No	No	14	
	Inception architecture	No	No		
	Computer architecture	Yes	No		
	Neural network*	No	No		
	Convolutional neural network	Yes	Yes		
	Convolutional codes	No	No		
	Total Index Terms	37			
	Shared Terms(*)	5			
	Unique Terms	32			
	Total OA Concepts Indexed	8			
	OA Concepts Used by OA	2			
OA Concepts Unused	6				

*denotes term that both group members indexed

(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?
2	MORBs	No	No
	Mid-ocean ridge basalts	No	No
	Mid-ocean ridge	Yes	No
	OIBs	No	No
	Ocean islands	No	No
	Basalt*	Yes	Yes
	Oceanic basalts	No	No
	Tectonics	Yes	Yes
	Chemical composition	Yes	Yes
	Isotope	Yes	No
	Systematic relationship	No	No
	Element concentrations	Yes	No
	Niobium	No	No
	Thermal erosion	No	No
	Sediment recycling	No	No
	Trace element	Yes	No
	Lithosphere	Yes	No
	Fractionation	Yes	No
	Magma	Yes	No
	Formation (geology)	No	No
	Subduction	Yes	Yes
	Mantle*	Yes	Yes
Total Index Terms		24	
Shared Terms(*)		2	
Unique Terms		22	
Total OA Concepts Indexed		12	
OA Concepts Used by OA		5	
OA Concepts Unused		7	

OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
Systematics	Mid-ocean ridge (3)
Basalt*	Trace element (2)
Mantle (geology)*	Lithosphere (3)
Geology	Fractionation (2)**
Geochemistry	Magma (3)
Oceanic crust	Isotope (2)
Earth science	Element concentrations (2)
Chemical composition	Terms That Should Be Concepts
Subduction	
Paleontology	n/a
Chemistry	Best OA Concepts
Biology	
Tectonics	Basalt (2)
Taxonomy (biology)	Mantle (2)
Botany	Chemical composition (2)
Organic chemistry	Subduction (3)
	Tectonics (2)
Total Concepts	** note that the concept 'Fractionation' is not suitable; refers to chemical properties rather than the geological process with the same name
16	
Total Suitable	
9	
Unsuitable	
7	

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(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?
3	Multimodal function	No	No
	Conductivity function	No	No
	<u>Hydraulic conductivity*</u>	Yes	Yes
	Soil hydraulic properties	No	No
	Soil water content	No	No
	<u>Soil water</u>	Yes	Yes
	<u>Water content</u>	Yes	Yes
	Simulated water flow	No	No
	<u>Pressure head</u>	Yes	Yes
	System curve	No	No
	Mualem-van Genuchten model	No	No
	<u>Soil science</u>	Yes	Yes
	Saturation	No	No
	<u>Water saturation</u>	Yes	No
	<u>Predictive modeling</u>	Yes	No
	<u>Closed form expression*</u>	Yes	No
	<u>Water retention*</u>	Yes	Yes
	<u>Geotechnical engineering</u>	Yes	No
	<u>Hydraulic head</u>	Yes	No
	<u>Groundwater flow equation</u>	Yes	No
Total Index Terms	23		
Shared Terms(*)	3		
Unique Terms	20		
Total OA Concepts Indexed	12		
OA Concepts Used by OA	7		
OA Concepts Unused	5		

OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
Hydraulic conductivity*	<i>Water saturation</i> (3)
Soil Water	<i>Predictive modeling</i> (2)
Conductivity	<i>Closed form expression*</i> (2)
Pressure head	<i>Hydraulic head</i> (2)
Soil science	<i>Groundwater flow equation</i> (5)
Water retention*	Terms That Should Be Concepts
Range (aeronautics)	
Water content	n/a
Materials science	Best OA Concepts
Mathematics	Hydraulic conductivity (3)
Geotechnical Engineering	Soil water (2)
Environmental Science	Pressure head (2)
Thermodynamics	Soil science (1)
Chemistry	Water retention (3)
Geology	Water content (2)
Physics	Geotechnical engineering (1)
Composite material	
Physical chemistry	
Total Concepts	
18	
Total Suitable	
9	
Unsuitable	
9	

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(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?	OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
4	Micropollutants*	No	No	Effluent	<i>Aquatic environment*</i> (2)
	Aquatic environment*	Yes	No	Nanofiltration	<i>Safe drinking water act</i> (3)
	Sewage	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Environmental Science	<i>Environmental impact assessment</i> (2)
	Surface water	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Sewage treatment	<i>Industrial wastewater treatment</i> (3)
	Groundwater	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Wastewater	
	Drinking water	Yes	No	Surface water	Terms That Should Be Concepts
	Wastewater treatment plants*	No	No	Sewage	
	WWTP	No	No	Environmental chemistry	
	Industrial wastewater treatment	Yes	No	Groundwater	Micropollutants*
	Effluent discharge	No	No	Water treatment	Wastewater treatment plants*
	Removal efficiency	No	No	Reverse osmosis	Best OA Concepts
	Activated carbon absorption	No	No	Water pollution	Nanofiltration (3)
	Oxidation processes	No	No	Environmental engineering	Surface water (2)
	Nanofiltration	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Chemistry	Sewage (2)
	Reverse osmosis	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Membrane	Groundwater (2)
	Membrane bioreactors	No	No	Biochemistry	Reverse osmosis (3)
	Fate modeling	No	No	Geotechnical Engineering	Wastewater (2)
	Environmental impact	Yes	No	Engineering	Water treatment (2)
	Physiochemical	No	No	Total Concepts	
	Advanced treatment processes	No	No	18	
	Micropollutant removal	No	No	Total Suitable	
	Total Index Terms	23		13	
	Shared Terms(*)	2		Unsuitable	
Unique Terms	21		5		
Total OA Concepts Indexed	9				
OA Concepts Used by OA	5				
OA Concepts Unused	4				

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(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?	OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
5	Geochemistry*	Yes	Yes	Groundwater*	<i>Carbon dioxide</i> (2)
	Groundwater*	Yes	Yes	Pollution*	<i>Ion exchange</i> (3)
	Pollution*	Yes	Yes	Geology	Terms That Should Be Concepts
	Hydrogeochemistry	No	No	Geochemistry*	
	Groundwater quality*	No	No	Environmental Science	Groundwater quality*
	Water-mineral Interaction	No	No	Water resource management	Water-mineral interaction /
	Water interaction	No	No	Mining engineering	Water interaction
	Modern hydrogeochemistry	No	No	Geotechnical Engineering	Best OA Concepts
	Rainwater	No	No	Ecology	
	Authoritative account	No	No	Biology	Pollution (2)
	Minerals	No	No		Geochemistry (1)
	Carbon dioxide	Yes	No		
	Ion exchange	Yes	No		
	Total Index Terms	17			
	Shared Terms(*)	4			
	Unique Terms	13			
	Total OA Concepts Indexed	5			
OA Concepts Used by OA	3				
OA Concepts Unused	2				
				Total Concepts	
				10	
				Total Suitable	
				4	
				Unsuitable	
				6	

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(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?	OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
6	<i>Pharmaceutically active compounds</i>	No	No	Effluent	<i>Pollution</i> (2)
	<i>Pharmaceutical residues</i>	No	No	Environmental chemistry*	<i>Sewage treatment</i> (2)
	<u>Aquatic environment*</u>	Yes	Yes	Glofibric acid	Terms That Should Be Concepts
	<u>Environmental chemistry*</u>	Yes	Yes	Aquatic environment*	
	Fate modeling	No	No	Surface water	Pharmaceutical compounds
	<u>Sewage</u>	Yes	Yes	Sewage	Pharmaceutical residues
	Pollution	Yes	No	Groundwater	Best OA Concepts
	Austria	No	No	Environmental science	Environmental chemistry (1)
	Brazil	No	No	Leachate	Aquatic environment (2)
	Canada	No	No	Groundwater recharge	Surface water (2)
	PHAC	No	No	Contamination	Sewage (2)
	Croatia	No	No	Subsoil	Groundwater (2)
	England	No	No	Chemistry	Leachate (2)
	Germany	No	No	Environmental engineering	Contamination (2)
	Greece	No	No	Biology	
	Italy	No	No	Ecology	
	Spain	No	No	Aquifer	
	Switzerland	No	No	Biochemistry	
	Drinking water samples	No	No	Geotechnical Engineering	
	<u>Leachate</u>	Yes	Yes	Soil water	
	<u>Groundwater</u>	Yes	Yes	Engineering	
	<i>Contaminants</i>	No	No	Soil science	
	<u>Contamination</u>	Yes	Yes	Total Concepts	
	<u>Surface water</u>	Yes	Yes	22	
	<i>Sewage treatment plants</i>	No	No	Total Suitable	
	<u>Sewage treatment</u>	Yes	No	16	
	Prescription drugs	No	No	Unsuitable	
	Drug metabolites	No	No	6	
	United States	No	No		
	Netherlands	No	No		
	Total Index Terms		32		
	Shared Terms(*)		2		
Unique Terms		30			
Total OA Concepts Indexed		9			
OA Concepts Used by OA		7			
OA Concepts Unused		2			

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(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?	OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
7	Field-scale dispersion	No	No	Aquifer*	<i>Hydraulics (2)</i>
	Data interpretation	No	No	Dispersion (optics)	<i>Flow (2)</i>
	Aquifer*	Yes	Yes	Transverse plane	<i>Porosity (2)</i>
	Dispersivity*	No	No	Scale (ratio)	<i>Effective porosity (3)</i>
	Field site	No	No	Geotechnical Engineering	Terms That Should Be Concepts
	Tracer test	No	No	Reliability (semiconductor)	
	Site (location)	No	No	Geology	
	Monitoring network	No	No	Environmental science	Best OA Concepts
	Hydraulics	Yes	No	Soil science	Aquifer* (3)
	<i>Hydraulic properties</i>	No	No	Hydrology (agriculture)	
	Flow	Yes	No	Groundwater	
	Flow configuration	No	No	Physics	
	Flow patterns	No	No	Engineering	
	Transverse dispersivity	No	No	Optics	
	Longitudinal dispersivity	No	No	Power (physics)	
	Dispersive mixing	No	No	Structural engineering	
	Porosity	Yes	No	Quantum mechanics	
	Effective porosity	Yes	No	Total Concepts	
	Aquifer heterogeneity	No	No	17	
	Total Index Terms	21		Total Suitable	
	Shared Terms(*)	2		7	
Unique Terms	19		Unsuitable		
Total OA Concepts Indexed	9		10		
OA Concepts Used by OA	5				
OA Concepts Unused	4				

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(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?	OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
8	<u>Slug test*</u>	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Aquifer	<i>Water well (3)</i>
	<u>Hydraulic conductivity*</u>	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Slug test	<i>Pressure head (2)</i>
	<u>Aquifer*</u>	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Hydraulic conductivity	<i>Groundwater flow (4)</i>
	Unconfined aquifer	No	No	Geotechnical engineering	<i>Groundwater flow equation (5)</i>
	Electrical resistance network analog	No	No	Geology	Terms That Should Be Concepts
	Water well	Yes	Yes	Aquifer test	
	<i>Penetrating well</i>	No	No	Specific storage	Thiem equation
	Rate of rise (Rise rate)	No	No	Hydraulic head	Steady state flow
	Transmissibility	No	No	Water table	Equilibrium water table
	Water level*	Yes	Yes	RADIUS	Best OA Concepts
	Volume	No	No	Water well	Aquifer (3)
	Piezometer method	No	No	Cone of depression	Slug test (4)
	Thiem equation*	No	No	Mechanics	Hydraulic conductivity (3)
	Steady state flow*	No	No	Soil science	Geotechnical engineering (1)
	Pressure head	Yes	No	Groundwater	Aquifer test (5)
	<i>Head loss</i>	No	No	Artesian aquifer	Hydraulic head (2)
	Equilibrium water table*	No	No	Groundwater recharge	Water table (3)
	Hydraulic head	Yes	Yes	Soil water	Water well (3)
	Auger hole method	No	No	Physics	
	Overlapping geometries	No	No	Computer security	
	Water table	Yes	Yes	Computer science	
	Aquifer test	Yes	Yes	Total Concepts	
	Geotechnical engineering	Yes	Yes	21	
	Groundwater flow	Yes	No	Total Suitable	
	Groundwater hydraulics	No	No	11	
	Groundwater flow equation	Yes	No	Unsuitable	
	Total Index Terms	33		10	
	Shared Terms(*)	7			
Unique Terms	26				
Total OA Concepts Indexed	12				
OA Concepts Used by OA	8				
OA Concepts Unused	4				

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(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?	OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
9	MODFLOW*	Yes	Yes	MODFLOW	<i>Groundwater flow equation (5)</i>
	<i>Flow equation</i>	No	No	Modular design	<i>Computer program (2)</i>
	Groundwater flow equation	Yes	No	Flow (mathematics)	<i>Finite difference method (2)</i>
	Groundwater	Yes	Yes	Computer science	Terms That Should Be Concepts
	Groundwater flow	Yes	Yes	Process (computing)	
	Computer program	Yes	No	Groundwater	n/a
	Geotechnical engineering	Yes	Yes	Applied mathematics	Best OA Concepts
	Porous medium	No	No	Groundwater flow	MODFLOW (5)
	Finite difference method	Yes	No	Mathematics	Groundwater (2)
	Enhancements	No	No	Geotechnical Engineering	Groundwater flow (4)
	Transport equation	No	No	Engineering	Geotechnical engineering (1)
	Parameter estimation	No	No	Programming language	
	Model calibration	No	No	Geometry	
	User's manual	No	No	Aquifer	
	Design concepts	No	No	Total Concepts	
	New package	No	No	14	
	Input instructions	No	No	Total Suitable	
	Flow model	No	No	13	
	Total Index Terms	19		Unsuitable	
	Shared Terms(*)	1		1	
Unique Terms	18				
Total OA Concepts Indexed	7				
OA Concepts Used by OA	4				
OA Concepts Unused	3				

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(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?	OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
10	<u>Evapotranspiration*</u>	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Evapotranspiration*</u>	<i>Catchment area</i> (3)
	Catchment scale	No	No	Groundwater recharge	<i>Catchment hydrology</i> (3)
	Catchment basin	No	No	Environmental science	<i>Land use</i> (2)
	Catchment area	Yes	No	Hydrology (agriculture)	<i>Land use planning</i> (3)
	Catchment hydrology	Yes	No	Water balance*	<i>Available water capacity</i> (4)
	<u>Drainage basin</u>	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Vegetation (pathology)	<i>Rational function</i> (2)
	Rational function	Yes	No	Interception	Terms That Should Be Concepts
	Empirical equation	No	No	Drainage basin	
	Climatic effects	No	No	Groundwater	
	<i>Vegetation changes</i>	No	No	Geography	Rainfall
	<i>Vegetation (ecology)</i>	No	No	Geology	Best OA Concepts
	Land use	Yes	No	Ecology	
	Land use planning	Yes	No	Aquifer	Groundwater recharge (4)
	Land use management	No	No	Medicine	Water balance (2)
	<u>Water balance*</u>	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Geotechnical Engineering	Drainage basin (2)
	Catchment water balance	No	No	Cartography	Geotechnical engineering (1)
	<u>Groundwater recharge</u>	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Pathology	
	<u>Geotechnical engineering</u>	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Biology	
	<i>Rainfall forecasting</i>	No	No	Total Concepts	
	<i>Rainfall</i>	No	No	18	
	Available water capacity	Yes	No	Total Suitable	
	Water yield modeling	No	No	12	
	Water yield	No	No	Unsuitable	
	Recharge estimation	No	No	6	
	Total Index Terms	26			
	Shared Terms(*)	2			
Unique Terms	24				
Total OA Concepts Indexed	11				
OA Concepts Used by OA	6				
OA Concepts Unused	5				

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(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?	OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
11	<i>Groundwater depletion*</i>	No	No	Groundwater recharge*	<i>Water stress (2)</i>
	Water stress*	Yes	No	Groundwater	<i>Geophysical fluid dynamics (2)</i>
	Aquifer	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Overexploitation	<i>Sea level rise (3)</i>
	Aquifer systems	No	No	Aquifer	<i>Water supply (2)</i>
	<i>Groundwater abstraction*</i>	No	No	Hydrology (agriculture)	<i>Environmental impact assessment (2)</i>
	Groundwater recharge*	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Environmental science	Terms That Should Be Concepts
	Overexploitation	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Depression-focused recharge	
	Geophysical fluid dynamics	Yes	No	Surface runoff	Best OA Concepts
	Groundwater	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Water resource management	
	Persistent groundwater depletion	No	No	Geology	Groundwater depletion*
	Global hydrological model	No	No	Ecology	Groundwater abstraction*
	Global water resources	No	No	Geotechnical Engineering	Groundwater recharge (4)
	Sea level rise	Yes	No	Biology	Groundwater (2)
	Water resource management	<u>Yes</u>	<u>Yes</u>	Total Concepts	Overexploitation (2)
	Water supply	Yes	No	13	Total Suitable
	Environmental impact assessment	Yes	No	Total Suitable	Aquifer (3)
	Total Index Terms	20		12	Water resource management (1)
	Shared Terms(*)	4		Unsuitable	
	Unique Terms	16		1	
	Total OA Concepts Indexed	10			
OA Concepts Used by OA	5				
OA Concepts Unused	5				

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(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?	OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused	
12	Groundwater flow*	Yes	Yes	Geology	<i>Water flow (2)</i>	
	<i>Small drainage basin</i>	No	No	Groundwater flow*	<i>Harmonic function (2)</i>	
	Drainage basin	Yes	Yes	Groundwater	<i>Basin and range topography (3)</i>	
	<i>Flow systems</i>	No	No	Hydrology (agriculture)		
	<i>Flow pattern</i>	No	No	Drainage	<i>Groundwater recharge (4)</i>	
	<i>Water flow systems</i>	No	No	Groundwater model	<i>Groundwater discharge (5)</i>	
	Water flow	Yes	No	Drainage basin	<i>Water level (2)</i>	
	Unconfined flow	No	No	Environmental science	Terms That Should Be Concepts	
	Hydrologic cycle	No	No	Aquifer		
	Homogeneous medium	No	No	Geotechnical Engineering	Topographic relief*	
	Harmonic function	Yes	No	Geography	Water flow systems /	
	Topographic relief*	No	No	Ecology	Water flow patterns	
	Subvertical boundary	No	No	Cartography	Best OA Concepts	
	Subhorizontal boundary	No	No	Biology	Geology (1)	
	Geology	Yes	Yes	Total Concepts	Groundwater flow (4)	
	Basin and range topography	Yes	No	14	Groundwater (2)	
	Groundwater	Yes	Yes	Total Suitable	Drainage basin (2)	
	Groundwater recharge	Yes	No	7		
	Groundwater discharge	Yes	No	Unsuitable		
	Water level	Yes	No	7		
	Total Index Terms	22				
	Shared Terms(*)	2				
Unique Terms	20					
Total OA Concepts Indexed	10					
OA Concepts Used by OA	4					
OA Concepts Unused	6					

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(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?	OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
13	Coastal ocean*	No	No	Brackish water	<i>Metal (2)</i>
	Groundwater	Yes	Yes	Groundwater	Terms That Should Be Concepts
	Groundwater flow	Yes	Yes	Submarine groundwater discharge	Coastal ocean*
	226Ra	No	No	Environmental science	226Ra (enrichments)*
	226Ra enrichments	No	No	Hydrology (agriculture)	River water flux*
	Seep meters	No	No	Seawater	Best OA Concepts
	South atlantic bight	No	No	Flux (metallurgy)	Brackish water (3)
	Groundwater discharge	Yes	Yes	Groundwater discharge	Groundwater (2)
	Groundwater input	No	No	Oceanography	Groundwater discharge (5)
	River water flux*	No	No	Groundwater flow	Groundwater flow (4)
	Terrestrial flux	No	No	Geology	<i>**although Flux is a concept and was indexed, the OpenAlex concept is specific to metallurgy and our group members were looking to index water flux</i>
	Flux**	Yes	Yes	Aquifer	
	Metal	Yes	No	Salinity	
	Nutrients	No	No	Geotechnical Engineering	
	Organic compounds	No	No	Materials science	
	Residence times	No	No	Metallurgy	
	Brackish water	Yes	Yes	Total Concepts	
	Coastal water	No	No	16	
	Regional scale	No	No	Total Suitable	
	Hydrological factors	No	No	11	
	Groundwater usage	No	No	Unsuitable	
	Sea level change	No	No	5	
	Total Index Terms	25			
Shared Terms(*)	3				
Unique Terms	22				
Total OA Concepts Indexed	6				
OA Concepts Used by OA	5				
OA Concepts Unused	1				

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(OA Level)

Article #	Group Member Index Terms	Exists in OA?	Used by OA?	OA Concepts	OA Concepts Unused
14	Groundwater recharge*	Yes	Yes	Groundwater recharge*	<i>Numerical modeling (2)</i>
	Groundwater recharge study	No	No	Hydrogeology	<i>Case study research (2)</i>
	Case study research	Yes	No	Aquifer*	<i>Water resource management (1)</i>
	Water resource evaluation	No	No	Hydrology (agriculture)	<i>Surface water (2)</i>
	Water resource management	Yes	No	Depression-focused recharge	<i>Groundwater contamination (4)</i>
	Water budget	No	No	Environmental science	<i>Aquifer properties (5)</i>
	Surface water	Yes	No	Groundwater	<i>Water flow (2)</i>
	Numerical modeling	Yes	No	Reliability (semiconductor)	Terms That Should Be Concepts
	Infiltration	No	No	Vadose zone	
	Diffuse recharge	No	No	Geology	n/a
	Arid regions	No	No	Geotechnical Engineering	Best OA Concepts
	Unsaturated zone	No	No	Power (physics)	
	Aquifer*	Yes	Yes	Physics	Groundwater recharge (4)
	Aquifer properties	Yes	No	Quantum mechanics	Aquifer (3)
	Water flow	Yes	No	Total Concepts	
	Time/space scale	No	No	14	
	Time scale	No	No	Total Suitable	
	Spatial scale	No	No	7	
	Groundwater contamination	Yes	No	Unsuitable	
	Groundwater recharge rate	No	No	7	
	Groundwater recharge estimate	No	No		
	Total Index Terms	23			
	Shared Terms(*)	2			
Unique Terms	21				
Total OA Concepts Indexed	9				
OA Concepts Used by OA	2				
OA Concepts Unused	7				